

COMPETENCY SKILLS AND PERFORMANCE LEVEL OF FACULTIES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION (HEI)

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Abstract:

One of the measures on the performance of the faculties is their competency levels and skills. This is true with their profession since teacher is the noblest among all professions. Teacher or lecturer involves challenges on their technical teaching as innovators to the young minds. The study examines the profile of the respondents and their competency skills and performance level of the faculty in the Higher Education Institutions ((HEI) in terms of communication, planning and administration, teamwork, strategic action, and self-management. The study employs quantitative descriptive approach and method of research because this approach collects the data that attempts in a quantifiable approach and information for statistical analysis of the competency skills and performance level of the faculties in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). Purposive sampling is utilized in the study because this kind of sampling is subjective, selective and judgmental in choosing the number of respondents needed in the study. It is a non-probability method used in choosing the population of the study. The subjects of the study are the different faculties in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). They are lecturers, module coordinators and program leaders. This is conducted for the period 2019-2020. The study comprised of thirty (30) respondents only. Results show that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their competency skills and performance level.

Keywords: competency skills, performance level, faculties in higher education institution (HEI), communication competency, planning and administrative competency, teamwork competency, strategic action competency, self-management competency

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1. Introduction

One of the measures on the performance of the faculties is their competency levels and skills. This is true with their profession since teacher is the noblest among all professions. Teacher or lecturer involves challenges on their technical teaching as innovators to the young minds. They can influence the life of their students giving positive reward and outlook in teaching among them, but the question is how? This is a challenge where their performance level and their competency skill will be measured particularly in the Higher Education Institution (HEI) to where they contribute much on the success of the mission and vision of the school (George, 2018).

Nevertheless, the competency skills and performance level of the faculties has many challenges just to equip with the latest trends of work in molding and shaping the future of the students. They have a standard to follow for their competency skills and performance level that can deliver a framework to assess students and to assist them the ability to think. Understanding the concept of their profession will challenge the faculties to adopt standard procedures on the latest trending of teaching to globally equip knowledge to improve learning enhancement of students toward self-direction, discipline by providing relevant information assessment, provide possible options and alternative in learning to open the minds of the students in their learning process and to be an effective and efficient individual as a whole (Paul, & Elder, 2019). This has been collaborated by (Nurius, & Kemp, 2019) on their study on the individual competency level which stressed on the domains of interrelationship like habits of the minds, knowledge, attitudes, values and skills that contributes to individuals discipline and distinction that influences and interacts with success in the training, tutoring, pastoring, facilitating, coaching in the different management in the discipline and conflict.

Subsequently, the communication skill is one of the competencies and performance skills that faculties need to develop and to explore. It provides perception to assess students on their role to play in the success of the academe. A better communication can open the minds of the students about their success in their educational attainment to prepare them for their economic and social aspect for them to achieve in life. The teacher roles as communicator to the skills of the students develop their integrity and potentials as youth and leaders in the future. This contributes to the achievement of students on their academics and performance (Khan, Khan, Zia-Ul-Islam, & Khan, 2017). Hence, it examines the evaluation and communication practices and measurement in the competency communication of the both the faculties and students. Professional competency skills develop and understand the conduct of individual party. Practice a better communication competency will reach your goal to accomplish your competency skills in the measurement of the communication benefits to the organization practices. This will highlight the skills in communication competency in the educational setting and other working environment. Techniques, decision-making and methods give a better insight in the communication competency skills (Zerfass, Verčič, & Volk, 2017). Furthermore, effective and efficient communication concisely and clearly defines communication competency skills and

performance level of individual. It will associate with faculty performance level association and leadership capacity and ability.

Consequently, planning and administration competency provides skills and performance of the faculties in the Higher Education and Institution (HEI). It helps them to delegate tasks and responsibilities on their profession. Anticipating the problems that might be encountered by them where skills and performance will be affected on their development plans to deal with students. There are several issues on their competency in terms of planning and administration as faculties. Monitoring students in their skills and learning would satisfy the performance of the faculties on their profession. Knowing and understanding the attitude and behavior of the students, challenge the patients of the faculties in their own way. Curriculum planning based on the needs of the students boost the morale of the faculties because they are giving solutions to students' needs, in their learning enhancement. Planning stipulates skills in the different classroom setting differentiating the skills and competencies of students that will put into practice. It will identify the needs adequate to address problems, skills, leadership, potentials of students, influencing the evidence based of learning. It reflects diversity in teaching, challenges, innovations in the practice of the improvement of learning among the students which illustrates approaches to the educational planning orientation and practices in the classroom setting and workplace to equip students (Ritchie, Sheppard, Croft, & Peel, 2017). Indeed, planning skills for faculties provides guidelines in their career as molders and shapers of students. Working as a team would pose a tasks on the result of their work output in the development level in educational profession (García-Carmona, Criado, & Cruz-Guzmán, 2017).

Furthermore, teamwork skills competency helps achieve the performance level of the faculties in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). The collaboration of teamwork in the workplace shows healthy environment and healthy working environment in the institution. It increases self-esteem and integrity among the faculties. Interventions are made based on the design enhancement that improves work tasks and improvement of the institution. This shows the effectiveness in the workplace or work area. Successful teamwork means projecting the outcome of the work desired establish by the institution for proper execution. This demonstrates the efficiency on the effectiveness of the process desired outcome of the tasks. Teamwork increases the interventions on the development and competencies on the effective process that leads to the improved desired outcome of the tasks. This is very timely to the domain across the institution that provides the adoption of training, and skills of every faculty in the institution. It provides a better understanding on the principle of teamwork to raise effectiveness in the working place in the Higher Education Institution (HEI) as mandated by their programme and domain (Lacerenza, Marlow, Tannenbaum, & Salas, 2018).

Likewise, strategic action is one of the competencies a faculty needs to develop as a measurement of their performance level in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). Realising and understanding the structure of the centers in the different institutions where priorities must be given emphasis through organisational strategies and goals

that leads to their mission and vision. The pressure on the faculties of the Higher Education Institution (HEI) considering the implication and decision on the operational goal strategy and the different approaches need strategic action plan to cultivate skills in a broader way. There is a need to identify the skills in the action plan and how to follow the action plan so with the development of the plan in the classroom setting. Strategic action includes competency management, intuition, resourcefulness and creativity, judgment based on the needs of the students, insights to where the strategic action is, and most of all the communication skills and social integrity of the students and the faculty as well (Grant, & Baden-Fuller, 2018).

Lastly, self-management competency must need to be addressed since this is important among the faculties of the Higher Education Institution (HEI). This shows perseverance on the part of the faculties in uplifting the learning process. The principle of self-management inside the classroom behavior facilitates teaching learning to condition of students. The concept is to provide better learning atmosphere among the students in identifying the major approaches to teaching in the achievement of the goal set in the teaching process. Consider the behavior of the students and consider the classroom environment where management must be the priority. The interaction of the students and availability of the students solely depends on the management technique a teacher established. Consider the behavior of the students as the center of learning (Glynn, 2017).

2. Statement of the Problem

1. How may the profile of the respondents be described in terms of their
 - 1.1 age,
 - 1.2 gender,
 - 1.3 educational attainment,
 - 1.4 years of service in the institution,
 - 1.5 position, and
 - 1.6 years of service in the present position?
2. What are the competency skills and performance level of the faculty respondents in the Higher Education Institutions ((HEI) in terms of
 - 2.1 communication,
 - 2.2 planning and administration,
 - 2.3 teamwork,
 - 2.4 strategic action, and
 - 2.5 self-management?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their competency skills and performance level?

2.1 Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their competency skills and performance level.

3. Research Method

The study employed the quantitative descriptive approach and method of research because this approach collects the data that attempts in a quantifiable approach and information for statistical analysis of the study. It describes and allows the segment of the study under investigated. It explains the analysis of the quantitative description on the competency skills and performance level of the faculties in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). It provided the formation methods of the different variables in the study (Zook, & Pearce, 2018).

3.1 Sampling Techniques

Purposive sampling is utilized in the study because this kind of sampling is subjective, selective and judgmental in choosing the number of respondents needed in the study. It is a non-probability method used in choosing the population of the study. This sampling represents the techniques in the selection of the respondents (Etikan, & Bala, 2017).

3.2 Subjects of the Study

The subjects of the study are the different faculties in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). They are lecturers, module coordinators and program leaders. This is conducted for the period 2019-2020. Thirty (30) respondents are utilized in the study. This validates the reliability and representation of the study under investigated.

3.3 Research Instrument

For purposes of data gathering, the research use a formatted questionnaire based on the details of the study using the following scale:

A. Competency skills and performance level of faculty in terms of communication.

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Outstanding	Communication competency performance of faculty is impressive.
3.40 – 4.19	Above Average	Communication competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.
2.80 – 3.39	Average	Communication competency performance of faculty is satisfactory.
1.80 - 2.79	Below Average	Communication competency performance of faculty is unsatisfactory.
1.00 – 1.79	Weak	Communication competency performance of faculty needs improvement.

B. Competency skills and performance level of faculty in terms of planning and administration

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Outstanding	Planning and administration competency performance of faculty is impressive.
3.40 – 4.19	Above Average	Planning and administration competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.
2.80 – 3.39	Average	Planning and administration competency performance of faculty is satisfactory.
1.80 - 2.79	Below Average	Planning and administration competency performance of faculty is unsatisfactory.
1.00 – 1.79	Weak	Planning and administration competency performance of faculty needs improvement.

C. Competency skills and performance level of faculty in terms of teamwork

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Outstanding	Teamwork competency performance of faculty is impressive.
3.40 – 4.19	Above Average	Teamwork competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.
2.80 – 3.39	Average	Teamwork competency performance of faculty is satisfactory.
1.80 - 2.79	Below Average	Teamwork competency performance of faculty is unsatisfactory.
1.00 – 1.79	Weak	Teamwork competency performance of faculty needs improvement.

D. Competency and performance level of faculty in terms of strategic action.

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Outstanding	Strategic action competency performance of faculty is impressive.
3.40 – 4.19	Above Average	Strategic action competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.
2.80 – 3.39	Average	Strategic action competency performance of faculty is satisfactory.
1.80 - 2.79	Below Average	Strategic action competency performance of faculty is unsatisfactory.
1.00 – 1.79	Weak	Strategic action competency performance of faculty needs improvement.

E. Competency and performance level of faculty in terms of self-management

Scale	Descriptive Level	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Outstanding	Self-management competency performance of faculty is impressive.
3.40 – 4.19	Above Average	Self-management competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.
2.80 – 3.39	Average	Self-management competency performance of faculty is satisfactory.
1.80 - 2.79	Below Average	Self-management competency performance of faculty is unsatisfactory.
1.00 – 1.79	Weak	Self-management competency performance of faculty needs improvement.

4. Results

Table 1: Profile of the respondents

Profile	<i>f</i>	%	<i>Ranking</i>
Age			
➤ 30 years and below	5	17	3
➤ 31-40 years old	8	27	2
➤ 41-50 years old	11	37	1
➤ 51-60 years old	4	13	4
➤ 61 years and above	2	7	5
Gender			
➤ Male	12	40	2
➤ Female	18	60	1
Educational Attainment			
➤ Bachelor's Degree	8	27	3
➤ MA Degree/Level	12	40	1
➤ Doctorate Degree/level	10	33	2
Years of Service in the Institution			
➤ 5 years and below	8	27	2.5
➤ 6-10 years	9	30	2
➤ 11-15 years	8	27	2.5
➤ 16-20 years	4	13	4
➤ 21 years and above	1	3	4
Position			
➤ Dean	3	10	5.5
➤ Head of Faculty	5	17	3.5
➤ Center Manager	3	10	5.5
➤ Program Leader	5	17	3.5
➤ Coordinator	7	23	1.5
➤ Lecturer	7	23	1.5
Years of Service in the Present Position			
➤ 1 year and below	5	17	4
➤ 2 years	3	10	5.5
➤ 3 years	6	20	2.5
➤ 4 years	3	10	5.5
➤ 5 years	6	20	2.5
➤ 6 years and above	7	23	1

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents, 41-50 years old age bracket, with a frequency of 11 or 37% among the respondents, female respondents, with a frequency of 18 or 60% among the respondents, educational attainment is MA degree and level with a frequency of 12 or 40% among the respondents, years of service in the institution is 6-10 years with a frequency of 9 or 30% among the respondents, position is coordinator and lecturer with a frequency of 7 or 27% among the respondents, and years of service in the present position is 6 years and above with a frequency of 7 or 23% among the respondents.

Table 2: Competency skills and performance level of faculty respondents
 in terms of communication competency

Indicators	WM	Interpretation	Ranking
1. Seeks out and listens to others who have contrary opinions.	4.17	Above Average	7.5
2. Makes people comfortable in different situations.	4.22	Outstanding	5
3. Varies communication approach when dealing with others from different background.	4.35	Outstanding	2
4. Builds strong interpersonal relationships with other people.	4.52	Outstanding	1
5. Shows genuine sensitivity to the feelings of others.	4.26	Outstanding	3
6. Informs people of events that are relevant to them.	4.22	Outstanding	5
7. Makes persuasive, high impact presentations before groups.	4.17	Above Average	7.5
8. Handles questions from the audience well.	4.22	Outstanding	5
Average Weighted Mean	4.27	Outstanding	
Standard Deviation	1.11		

Table 2 shows the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on the communication competency of the respondents. Builds strong interpersonal relationships with other people with (WM=4.52) is outstanding which means communication competency performance of faculty is impressive, varies communication approach when dealing with others from different background with WM=4.35 which means communication competency performance of faculty is impressive, shows genuine sensitivity to the feelings of others with (WM=4.26) is outstanding which means communication competency performance of faculty is impressive, makes people comfortable in different situations, informs people of events that are relevant to them and handles questions from the audience well with (WM=4.22) is outstanding which means communication competency performance of faculty is impressive, and seeks out and listens to others who have contrary opinions and makes persuasive, high impact presentations before groups with (WM=4.17) is above average which means communication competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory. The overall (AWM=4.27) is outstanding which means communication competency performance of faculty is impressive.

Table 3: Competency skills and performance level of faculty respondents
 in terms of planning and administration competency

Indicators	WM	Interpretation	Ranking
1. Monitors information that is relevant to on-going projects and activities.	4.22	Outstanding	3
2. Obtains and uses relevant information to identify symptoms and underlying problems.	4.09	Above Average	5
3. Makes decisions on time.	4.30	Outstanding	1.5
4. Anticipates negative and positive consequences.	4.17	Above Average	4
5. Knows when expert knowledge is needed and seeks it out to solve problems.	3.74	Above Average	8
6. Develops plans and schedules to achieve specific goals efficiently.	4.30	Outstanding	1.5
7. Prioritises tasks in order to stay focused on those that are most important.	4.00	Above Average	7
8. Organises people around specific tasks to help them work together on a common objective.	4.04	Above Average	6
Average Weighted Mean	4.11	Above Average	
Standard Deviation	1.54		

Table 3 shows the core competency skills and performance level of faculty respondents in terms of planning and administration competency, makes decisions on time and develops plans and schedules to achieve specific goals efficiently with (WM=4.30) is outstanding which means planning and administration competency performance of faculty is impressive, monitors information that is relevant to on-going projects and activities with (WM=4.22) is outstanding which means planning and administration competency performance of faculty is impressive, anticipates negative and positive consequences with (WM=4.17) is above average which means planning and administration competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, obtains and uses relevant information to identify symptoms and underlying problems (WM=4.09) is above average which means planning and administration competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, organises people around specific tasks to help them work together on a common objective with (WM=4.04)) is above average which means planning and administration competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, prioritises tasks in order to stay focused on those that are most important with (WM=4.00) is above average which means planning and administration competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory and knows when expert knowledge is needed and seeks it out to solve problems with (WM=3.74) is above average which means planning and administration competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory. The overall (AWM=4.11) is above average which means planning and administration competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.

Table 4: Competency skills and performance level of faculty respondents in terms of teamwork competency

Indicators	WM	Interpretation	Ranking
1. Formulates clear goals that inspire team members' commitment.	4.13	Above Average	3.5
2. Selects team members appropriately, taking into account diversity of viewpoints and technical skills.	4.04	Above Average	6
3. Provides team members with clear vision of what is to be accomplished by the team.	3.96	Above Average	7.5
4. Creates a process for monitoring team performance.	3.96	Above Average	7.5
5. Assigns tasks and responsibilities to individual team members consistent with their competencies and interest.	4.13	Above Average	3.5
6. Creates a team setting in which team members feel that their suggestions make a difference.	4.22	Outstanding	2
7. Recognises, praises, and rewards team members for their contributions.	4.09	Above Average	5
8. Assists the team in acquiring the resources and support it needs to accomplish its goals.	4.26	Outstanding	1
Average Weighted Mean	4.10	Above Average	
Standard Deviation	1.57		

Table 4 shows the core competency skills and performance level of faculty respondents in terms of teamwork, assists the team in acquiring the resources and support it needs to accomplish its goals with (WM=4.26) is outstanding which means teamwork

competency performance of faculty is impressive, creates a team setting in which team members feel that their suggestions make a difference with (WM=4.22) is outstanding which means teamwork competency performance of faculty is impressive, formulates clear goals that inspire team members' commitment and assigns tasks and responsibilities to individual team members consistent with their competencies and interest with (WM=4.13) is above average which means teamwork competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, recognises, praises, and rewards team members for their contributions with (WM=4.09) is above average which means teamwork competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, selects team members appropriately, taking into account diversity of viewpoints and technical skills with (WM=4.04) is above average which means teamwork competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, provides team members with clear vision of what is to be accomplished by the team and creates a process for monitoring team performance with (WM=3.96) is above average which means teamwork competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory. The overall ((AWM=4.10) is above average which means teamwork competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.

Table 5: Competency skills and performance level of faculty respondents in terms of strategic action competency

Indicators	WM	Interpretation	Ranking
Understands the history of industry of which the organization is a part.	3.87	Above Average	5.5
Stays informed of the actions of competitors and strategic partners in the academic milieu of which the organization is a part.	4.04	Above Average	2
Analyses general trends and understands their implications for the future.	3.91	Above Average	4
Recognises quickly when significant changes occur in the institution.	3.83	Above Average	7.5
Knows how organisation competes in the global market.	3.83	Above Average	7.5
Understand the concerns of all major stakeholders of the organization.	3.87	Above Average	5.5
Understands the strengths and limitations of various management strategies.	4.00	Above Average	3
Knows the distinctive strengths of the organization.	4.09	Above Average	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.99	Above Average	
Standard Deviation	1.21		

Table 5 shows the competency skills and performance level of faculty respondents in terms of strategic action competency, knows the distinctive strengths of the organization with (WM=4.09) is above average which means strategic action competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, stays inform of the actions of competitors and strategic partners in the academic milieu of which the organization is a part with (WM=4.04) is above average which means strategic action competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, understands the strengths and limitations of various management strategies with (WM=4.00) is above average which means strategic

action competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, analyses general trends and understand their implications for the future with (WM=3.91) is above average which means strategic action competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, understands the history of industry of which the organization is a part and understand the concerns of all major stakeholders of the organization with (WM=3.87) is above average which means strategic action competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, recognises quickly when significant changes occur in the institution and knows how organisation competes in the global market with (WM=3.83) is above average which means strategic action competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory. The overall (AWM=3.99) is above average which means strategic action competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.

Table 6: Competency skills and performance level of faculty respondents in terms of self-management competency

Indicators	1	2	3
Clears personal standards that serve as a foundation for maintaining a sense of integrity and ethical conduct.	3.61	Above Average	7
Maintains personal ethical standards under fire.	3.09	Average	8
Projects self-assurance sincerity, doesn't just tell people what they want to hear.	3.83	Above Average	6
Recognises own mistakes and admits to having made them.	3.96	Above Average	5
Accepts own responsibility for own actions.	4.13	Above Average	2
Seeks responsibility beyond what is required by the job.	4.13	Above Average	2
Innovates willingly and take personal risks.	4.00	Above Average	4
Motivates ambitiously to achieve the goals.	4.13	Above Average	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.86	Above Average	
Standard Deviation	1.23		

Table 6 shows the competency skills and performance level of faculty respondents in terms of self-management competency, accepts own responsibility for own actions, seeks responsibility beyond what is required by the job and motivates ambitiously to achieve the goals with (WM=4.13) is above average which means self-management competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, recognises own mistakes and admits to having made them with (WM=3.83) is above average which means self-management competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, clears personal standards that serve as a foundation for maintaining a sense of integrity and ethical conduct with (WM=3.61) is above average which means self-management competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory, and maintains personal ethical standards under fire with (WM=3.09) is average which means self-management competency performance of faculty is satisfactory. The overall (AWM=3.86) is above average which means self-management competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.

Table 7: Significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their competency skills and performance level

Variable	Computed r-value	Relationships *significant * not significant	Hypotheses *accepted *rejected
Age			
1. Communication	0.302	not significant	accepted
2. Planning and Administration	0.031	not significant	accepted
3. Teamwork	0.031	not significant	accepted
4. Strategic Action	0.323	not significant	accepted
5. Self-Management	0.033	not significant	accepted
Gender			
1. Communication	0.018	not significant	accepted
2. Planning and Administration	0.019	not significant	accepted
3. Teamwork	0.019	not significant	accepted
4. Strategic Action	0.020	not significant	accepted
5. Self-Management	0.020	not significant	accepted
Educational Attainment			
1. Communication	0.028	not significant	accepted
2. Planning and Administration	0.029	not significant	accepted
3. Teamwork	0.029	not significant	accepted
4. Strategic Action	0.030	not significant	accepted
5. Self-Management	0.031	not significant	accepted
Years of Service in the Institution			
1. Communication	0.037	not significant	accepted
2. Planning and Administration	0.038	not significant	accepted
3. Teamwork	0.038	not significant	accepted
4. Strategic Action	0.040	not significant	accepted
5. Self-Management	0.041	not significant	accepted
Position			
1. Communication	0.048	not significant	accepted
2. Planning and Administration	0.049	not significant	accepted
3. Teamwork	0.049	not significant	accepted
4. Strategic Action	0.051	not significant	accepted
5. Self-Management	0.052	not significant	accepted
Year of Service in Present Position			
1. Communication	0.024	not significant	accepted
2. Planning and Administration	0.025	not significant	accepted
3. Teamwork	0.025	not significant	accepted
4. Strategic Action	0.025	not significant	accepted
5. Self-Management	0.026	not significant	accepted

Significant at 0.05 level, one-tailed test, df at 21 with critical r-value of 0.413

Table shows that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their competency skills and performance level since the computed r when tested against each variables show the result is lower than the critical r value of 0.413, which means the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

5. Discussion

Profile of the respondents shows their competency skills and their performance level. It indicates here that most of the respondents are on their stablish stage since they are on their onset of life which reveals maturity in handling their task as educators in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). Most of the respondents are female which reveals that female respondents have the passion in teaching, dedicated and flexible in the learning process where their competency skills and performance level are impressive. Nonetheless, most of them have attained Master's degree where, they develop their competency skills and performance level in exercising their profession as molders and shapers of students. They have been in the service or teaching for 6 to 10 years which reveals that they have much exposure in the skills on the learning process. Position for them is not a matter what important is they inculcate values and inject learning process to achieve students' enhancement though their positions are coordinators and lecturers. It emphasizes in the result of the study that most of them are 6 years and above in their present position which shows they are experienced enough and have the competency skills on their performance as educators in the Higher Education Institution (HEI). It provides leadership evidence on competency and performance motivation in the institution goals and objectives on the mission and vision provided by all faculties under their jurisdiction. The relationship between the competency skills of the profile of the respondents from their performance level explains their efficiency and effectiveness of their performance and their role as educators in the institution (Rahardja, Moein, & Lutfiani, 2018).

In addition, communication competency shows outstanding which means impressive because it is their line of expertise. They have learnt many techniques and strategies in dealing with their students. They build a strong interpersonal relationship with other people and have a strong edge in dealing with other people and are confident in their communication process and skills. Similarly, their communication approaches vary depends on the level of the students. They can adopt situation where they can reach students to the best way they can. Also, they show genuine sensitivity to the feelings of others which means they are concern about their students' ability and capacity in dealing with them. Communicative competency prevail theories in learning among the students in the classroom as guide for evaluation and teaching performance level of the lecturers based on support, construction, and empirical goal of institution context in classroom setting in many different approaches (Savignon, 2018).

Meanwhile, on the planning and administrative competency reveals above average which means planning and administration competency of faculties in the Higher Education Institution (HEI) performance level is very satisfactory since the respondents' shows they are quick in making decision on time and based on the needs of the students in their classroom. They also develop plan and schedule to achieve specific goals as faculties in the institution which leads them to attain their work efficiently and effectively. Planning is important to develop since it is a part of their goal to have a better output in the classroom setting. Also, monitors information that is

needed or relevant to their activities, projects, homework or other activities needed in the school. They also have the attitude to know and identify the negative and feedback on their plans as a challenge on their part and as a part of future improvement. Teachers planning and administration provides development and competence of a faculty for delivery of services and improvement. This is adopted on the standard procedures to be followed by all faculties. Teachers planning competency help to develop their skills in communication, management, planning the lessons and attributes to their professional growth. The planning adequacy provides direction for goals to be achieved. They are determined to ensure the learners' needs tailored to the vision and mission of the school. Planning properly among the teachers facilitates resources implementation successfully on the purpose designation. Administratively planning are responsible integration and designation programs for teachers deficiency to address in their areas of specialization directing teachers education in terms of teaching and facilities (Ukaigwe, & Igbozuruike, 2019).

Nevertheless, on the teamwork competency, it reveals above average which means that teamwork competency of faculties is very satisfactory. Hence, the respondents have the capacity to assist the team in acquiring the resources and support needed to accomplish the goals. They are teamwork individual towards the goal of the institution. On the other hand, they can create a team setting in which members feel their suggestions that make a difference. They are there not only a support to the team but they can also suggest for better improvement of the institution. They believe that two heads are better than one. In addition, they can formulate clear goals that inspire team members and commitment. They are committed and dedicated to their profession as faculties. Certainly, they can also do the tasks being given to them with little supervision and they are responsible at individual team according to their competence and interest. Teamwork competency core in the learning process is a skill where everybody can be benefitted. Hence, teamwork assessment is a complex measure in developing a domain applicable to the learners. It is a technology that provides and helps assessment of teamwork formation because it entails peer and self-rating on the methods of pedagogy measure of teamwork. Teamwork program and awareness incorporates among their curriculum and knowledge of self-discipline, projects and work. Students' programmed is described as their experiences as faculties in the institution. The dimension of the competency teamwork serves as support to their emotional teamwork engagement, awareness and reflection practices to the educational world of knowledge and learning (Koh, Hong, & Tan, 2018). Similarly, teamwork needs aspect in their world of work. It is an extensive knowledge as part of their growth as institutional molders of the learners outcome related team, and process. It reflects to develop theories in aspect of multilayered team as basis of their teamwork competency. Recognising the stronger collective individual initiation tasks as a team, definitely the team is formed equally and therefore, important consideration on team relevant to the dynamic understanding in a content outcome. Teamwork performs different formation and critically supportive in the environment organization and condition to flourish and resolve the mechanics of conflicts. This also ensures safety, and performance

improvement. Therefore, competency in teamwork helps on the increase efficiency and effectiveness of work identified among them. It is worthy to note that teamwork competency is the result of coordination, communication and cooperation among the members of the group who works together. This has ensured the improve maintenance of teamwork function effectively in the organization that implements the intervention and development relevant to evaluate teamwork measures. This has addressed problems of teamwork for improve assessment, system of teamwork and identify the gap between actual practices from theories and actualisation (Salas, Reyes, & McDaniel, 2018).

Moreover, the result of strategic action planning competency shows above average which means that respondents strategic action planning competency is very satisfactory. They stressed that they know the distinct strengths in the organization in which they know how to adjust and attack the action plan as based on the set achieve goals in the institution. This can help them improve their competency skills and competency level on their profession as molders of the learners to better equip in their role as faculties in the institution and to globally competent in the field of education. Elsewhere, stays inform in the action of competition and strategic partners in the academe. Their ultimate goal is to contribute in the success of the Higher Education Institution (HEI) or organization regarding their competency skills and performance level. Though they have their limitations and strengths in the various different strategies in management, hence; the approach in the competency base highlights in the cornerstone of the education. It describes the competency approach classification and actual practice experiences (Rubin, Lednev, & Mozhzhukhin, 2018). Effective strategic action plan cope with changes of the improve system in the operation of the organisation. It develops a better design to improve quality education as learners as the center of their target. Also, they need to respond future challenges in the organisation to be globally competent in the field of education. Strategic action plan must have extensive analysis that can set deliberately on the process of the organisation. It helps the administration, managers and leaders and head to address the different challenges in the institution. It analyses, gathers a significant strategic plans for producing judgment to initiate the process and system in the institution (Bryson, 2018).

Certainly, on the result of the self-management competency shows above average in which self-management competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory. This has been proven because they accept responsibility of their own action which means they are responsible in what they perform in the institution base on the standard operation of the organisation. Yet, they even seek responsibility beyond what is required of the job. This emphasises their dedication, flexibility, resourcefulness of what they are doing. They even explore their job because they are passionate in their teaching profession. They are indeed motivated ambitiously to achieve and contribute to the success of the institution. Addressing the work balance and life gap focus on intervention approaches to elicit and to inform self-management use and behaviors draw a competent base knowledge, relevant to skills framework and abilities. Self-management face challenges in their work and interfaces life on the demands of their

work against their job description initiatives. The framework and competency provides flexibility expectation on their management boundaries among themselves. It focuses on their strategies and behaviors towards effective self-management competency (McDowall, & Lindsay, 2014).

6. Conclusions

It shows that profile of the respondents are knowledgeable enough in their role as faculties in the Higher Education Institution (HEI) partners in molding and shaping the future of their children since they are matured enough in their job and experiences. They have the mastery of their job that can make them competent in their performance level. They have been working for a decade to help them improve the system for quality education among their recipients.

It shows that communication competency is above average which means communication competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory. Planning and administration competency shows above average which means planning competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory. Teamwork competency shows above average which means teamwork competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory. Strategic action competency shows above average which means strategic action planning competency of faculty is very satisfactory and self-management competency shows above average which means self-management competency performance of faculty is very satisfactory.

However, there is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their competency skills and performance level since the computed r when tested against each variables show the result is lower than the critical r value of 4.13, which the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

6.1 Recommendations

- 1) Profile of the respondents should explore more on the upgrade of their knowledge in the competency skills through seminars and workshop on the performance level achievement and competency techniques to equip with the global trending on the educational strategies in handling learners in the Higher Education Institution (HEI).
- 2) Communication competency skills must seek out and listen to people on their good opinion and make persuasion and high impact in the communication process. Planning and administration must be given emphasis to improve the educational system in solving issues in the institution. Teamwork should have a clear vision of what to be accomplished because two heads are better than one. Strategic action competency should recognize the significant changes in the institution or organisation to compete with the educational setting and self-management competency to maintain personal standard ethics in the future.
- 3) Since, there is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their competency skills and performance level there must be a continues

study on the competency skills and performance level of the respondents like upgrade on the knowledge of skills in the teaching job, competency level, and student to teacher relationship this will equip a better knowledge in the competency level of the faculties in the Higher Education Institution (HEI).

References

- Bryson, J. M. (2018). *Strategic planning for public and nonprofit organizations: A guide to strengthening and sustaining organizational achievement*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Etikan, I., & Bala, K. (2017). Sampling and sampling methods. *Biometrics & Biostatistics International Journal*, 5(6), 00149.
- García-Carmona, A., Criado, A. M., & Cruz-Guzmán, M. (2017). Primary pre-service teachers' skills in planning a guided scientific inquiry. *Research in Science Education*, 47(5), 989-1010.
- George, K. E., 2018. The Challenge of Being a Technical Teacher. *IJASSH*.
- Glynn, T. (2017). Building an effective teaching environment. In *Psychological aspects of learning and teaching* (pp. 40-59). Routledge.
- Grant, R. M., & Baden-Fuller, C. (2018). How to develop strategic management competency: Reconsidering the learning goals and knowledge requirements of the core strategy course. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 17(3), 322-338.
- Khan, A., Khan, S., Zia-Ul-Islam, S., & Khan, M. (2017). Communication Skills of a Teacher and Its Role in the Development of the Students' Academic Success. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(1), 18-21.
- Koh, E., Hong, H., & Tan, J. P. L. (2018). Formatively assessing teamwork in technology-enabled twenty-first century classrooms: exploratory findings of a teamwork awareness programme in Singapore. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 38(1), 129-144.
- Lacerenza, C. N., Marlow, S. L., Tannenbaum, S. I., & Salas, E. (2018). Team development interventions: Evidence-based approaches for improving teamwork. *American Psychologist*, 73(4), 517.
- McDowall, A., & Lindsay, A. (2014). Work-life balance in the police: The development of a self-management competency framework. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 29(3), 397-411.
- Nurius, P. S., & Kemp, S. P. (2019). Individual-Level Competencies for Team Collaboration with Cross-Disciplinary Researchers and Stakeholders. In *Strategies for Team Science Success* (pp. 171-187). Springer, Cham.
- Paul, R., & Elder, L. (2019). *A guide for educators to critical thinking competency standards: Standards, principles, performance indicators, and outcomes with a critical thinking master rubric*. Rowman & Littlefield.

- Rahardja, U., Moein, A., & Lutfiani, N. (2018). Leadership, Competency, Working Motivation and Performance of High Private Education Lecturer with Institution Accreditation B: Area Kopertis IV Banten Province. *Man India*, 97(24), 179-192.
- Ritchie, H., Sheppard, A., Croft, N., & Peel, D. (2017). Planning education: exchanging approaches to teaching practice-based skills. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 54(1), 3-11.
- Rubin, Y., Lednev, M., & Mozhzhukhin, D. (2018). Entrepreneurship education in action: a matrix of competencies for a bachelor's degree program. In *Annals of Entrepreneurship Education and Pedagogy–2018* (p. 187). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Salas, E., Reyes, D. L., & McDaniel, S. H. (2018). The science of teamwork: Progress, reflections, and the road ahead. *American Psychologist*, 73(4), 593.
- Savignon, S. J. (2018). Communicative competence. *The TESOL encyclopedia of English language teaching*, 1-7.
- Ukaigwe, P. C., & Igbozuruike, I. U. (2019). Planning: A Tool for Administration of Teachers' Competence Development Programmes for Improved Service Delivery in Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 6(1).
- Zerfass, A., Verčič, D., & Volk, S. C. (2017). Communication evaluation and measurement: Skills, practices and utilization in European organizations. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 22(1), 2-18.
- Zook, K. L., & Pearce, J. H. (2018). Quantitative descriptive analysis. In *Applied Sensory Analy of Foods* (pp. 43-71). Routledge.

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